

Jain Temples of Murshidabad

Balagnath Bhattacharyya

Ex-Dy General Manger (Finance), Damodar Valley Corporation- a PSU

Email: bhattacharyyabn@gmail.com

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Abstract

First phase of Jainism entered Bengal along with Buddhism or slightly earlier in the fourth and third century BCE and continued up to the seventh century CE as reported by Yuan Chowang (Hiuen Tsang) in his travelogue. Thereafter due to the flourishing of Buddhism and Hinduism and diminishing royal patronage it gradually withered away. In the second phase, Jainism again flourished in the western part of Bengal in the eleventh century during the reign of Kalinga King Anant Burman Chodaganga Deva, ruler of the Eastern Ganga dynasty of Odisha. A large number of Jain temples were constructed during his reign in the areas of Bankura, Purulia West Bardhaman, and West Birbhum of Bengal. The descendants of Anant Barman also patronized Jainism and encouraged the building of Jain temples. But following the 12th century, Jainism declined due to the overwhelming influence of Brahminic religion during the Sena period. Again, in the eighteenth-century Jainism again flourished in the District of Murshidabad in West Bengal through Jain Merchants. In 1704 CE Seth Manick Chand predecessor of Jagat Seths, a great merchant and moneylender came to Murshidabad from Dhaka along with Kartalab Khan (Murshid Kuli Khan), Diwan of Bengal who shifted his headquarters to Murshidabad from Dhaka, the then capital of Bengal due to severe dispute with Nayeb Nazim Azim Us Shan. Being a Devout Jain Seth Manikchand established the foundation of Jainism in Murshidabad. Along with his residential palaces, he built Jain temples there. Subsequently, various Jain merchants of Rajasthan of different clans came to the area in the latter half of the eighteenth century and constructed several beautiful Jain temples at Murshidabad, Jiaganj, and Ajimganj which form three corners of a geographical triangle –river Bhagirathi longitudinally inside. This triangular area containing about 17/18 temples on both sides of the river Ganges became so popular to the entire Jain community throughout India that it was beginning to be called ‘Murshidabad Tirth’ by Jains.

Key Words: Jainism, Jain Temples, Jain Merchants, Murshidabad, Jagat Seth, Murshidabad Tirth

Introduction

Jainism in Bengal

Jainism is the first Aryan religion that came to Bengal during the Maurya period. Several Jain religious scriptures mentioned the places of Pundravardhana, Banga, Ladh (Radha) as the centers of Jain religion in Bengal. In Acharanga Sutra it is stated that 'once Mahavir (599 BCE to 527 BCE), founder of Jain religion came to Ladh Desha (Rarh of Bengal) along with his disciples. There he was severely insulted by the locals even there is an anecdote that people set the dogs on Mahavira. It proves that local people did not accept Jainism easily. However, this resistance weakened subsequently. As stated by Dr. Nihar Ranjan Ray by 4th and 3rd century BCE Jain religion spread over North Bengal or Pundravardhan. in Brihat Katha Kosh of Harisashena it is mentioned that Guru of Maurya emperor Chandragupta famous Jain suri Bhadrabahu was the son of a Brahmin of Debakot under Pundra Vardhan (Ray, 1903 : 493). Moreover, Jain Kalpa sutra scriptures mentioned about four branches of Godas Jain Bhikkhus. The names of the four branches are Tamalittya, Kodibarshiya, Pongdabardhaniya, and Kharbat. All these were place names of Bengal – respectively Tamralipta, Kotibarsha, Pundravardhan and Kharbat. There are further pieces of evidence regarding the existence of Jainism up to the second century CE. Thereafter due to the advent of Brahminic Hinduism and Buddhism patronized by kings and emperors, Jainism took a back seat (Ray, 1903 : 493). Despite that, according to the evidence furnished by Yuan Chawang (Hiu en Sung) as mentioned in his travelogue, in the 7th century CE (629 -643 CE) there is a substantial number of 'Nirgrantha Jain' in Bengal. According to his account maximum number of monks present in Pundrabardhan were Digambar Jains (naked Nirgranthas,). Same is with Samatata – here also the maximum number of monks were naked Nirgrantha. In respect of the other two places visited by Huyen Sung – Karna Suvarna and Tamralipta, He said that there are a substantial number of non-Buddhists. Those might be Brahminic Hindus, Jains, Ajeebiks, and other minor religious followers (Ray, 1956: 96, 100). But Dr. Nihar Ranjan Ray cast doubt over the statistics given by Hieun Tsang. He stated that Hieun Tsang mixed up Jains with those of the Ajivika sect.

Second Phase

However, during Pala Period the influence of Jainism receded but again flourished in the last centuries of Pala rule during the 10th - 11th century CE in western West Bengal in Purulia, Bankura Western part of Birbhum and Bardhaman. Several Jain temples were constructed during the period. The existence of Pareshnath hill nearby a great pilgrimage of Jains, where twenty of twenty- four Tirthankaras of Jain religion took nirvana appeared to be the reason behind it. From Pareshnath hill Jain religion spread up to present-day Chhattishgarh crossing the highly forested

lands. However, to Bengal Jain religious preachers came through the river Damodar, Kangsabati, Silabati, Darakeswar

rivers. But construction of Jain temples in and around the area reached a great height during the period of King Anant Burman Chodaganga Deva.

Around 1078 CE the region came under the control of Kalinga King Anant Burman Chodaganga Deva, ruler of the eastern Ganga dynasty of Odisha. This was Jainism's golden age in the area. Though a Shaivite himself Ananta Burman was a great patroniser of Jainism and built many Jain temples around Ambika Nagar (in present Bankura District), his second capital. His successors also continued to patronize Jainism and as a result, a large number of magnificent Jain temples came up in Bankura and Purulia in the 11th and 12th centuries. But following the 12th century, Jainism declined due to the overwhelming influence of Brahminic religion during the Sena period, and the shrines were either abandoned or were began to be worshipped as Hindu temples. The existing gods and goddesses were considered as Hindu Gods and Goddesses or New stone images of Hindu gods and goddesses were installed in the temples (Gupta, 2020). After the 12th century, Jainism practically disappeared from the religious scenario of Bengal except a community called 'Sharak' previously known as

'Shrabaka which still exists though sparingly in Bengal, Jharkhand, Odisha, and Bihar who follow Jainism.

Third Phase

However, again curtain was raised in the eighteenth-century CE. (O'Malley, 1914 :58-69, 75).

Jainism appeared in the Murshidabad District of Bengal through merchant bankers, traders, and fortune seekers of Rajasthan. These Jain communities came to Murshidabad in two phases. The first phase is between 1700 to 1765 CE when the Jagat Seth family and their relatives from Marwar, Rajasthan came to Bengal first in Dhaka and thereafter in Murshidabad in 1703 CE. And a second wave came after 1765 after the fall of Jagatseths when the mantle of Jain community of Bengal passed on to other Jain merchant clans like Dugars, Nahars, Singh is etc (Doogar, <http://faculty.washington.edu/doogar/Research/mbd.pdf>).

Jains in Murshidabad

Entry and Rise of Jagat Seths

One Hiranand Gailara or Galera, a resident of the town of Nagaur of the Marwar region of Rajasthan and a trader, facing hard times there, migrated to Patna, the seat of Mughal

administration in Bihar to seek fortune. In course of time, Hiranand became a successful banker and a saltpeter merchant at Patna. He had six sons each of them was successful traders. The fourth son, Manikchand, moved to Dhaka the capital of Subah Bengal under the Mughal administration, at the end of seventeenth century, and began his money lending business and also began to work under Kartalab Khan the then Diwan of Bengal. But soon Diwan fell out with the then viceroy of Bengal Azim Us Shan (grandson of Emperor Aurangzeb) and he left Dhaka and came to Mukhsudabad. Kartalab Khan was liked very much by Aurangzeb due to his past performances in the battleground of Deccan. In 1704 CE he was made Nayeab Nazim and awarded the title of Murshid Kuli Khan and the city of Mukshudabad was renamed as Murshidabad after his name and endorsed by Aurangzeb. Manikchand was closely aligned – both politically and personally – with Nawab Murshid Quli Khan. Manikchand was appointed deputy diwan, tasked with the organization and supervision of revenue collection and the treasury, and later with the administration of the Murshidabad Mint (Doogar, <http://faculty.washington.edu/doogar/Research/mbd.pdf> : 14). Seth Manickchand with his business acumen and strong connection with administration became one of the wealthiest persons in the world during the period. In 1717 CE Murshid Kuli Khan was appointed as Nawab of Bengal province by Mughal Emperor Farrukshiar and Murshidabad became the capital. The status of Manikchand was also elevated and he became personal banker to Murshid Quli Khan with whom he was jointly credited in having invested heavily to ensure the development of Murshidabad and its environs (Doogar, <http://faculty.washington.edu/doogar/Research/mbd.pdf> : 16). The financial prowess of Manikchand as the chief of Murshidabad Mint and Treasury of Bengal as well as his financial strength was well known to Mughal Court. Mughal court was well aware of the fact that the wheel of the entire Mughal administration is revolving only due to the huge revenue coming from Bengal province only [One crore fifty lakh silver rupiah annually- Rs 19 billion in today's value (Dalrymple, 2019: 34)] due to machination of Seth

Manikchand. As recognition of Seth Manikchand's prowess and depth of financial richness Mughal emperor Farrukhshiyar (1713-19) conferred him the title of 'Jagat Seth' –Banker of the world (Dalrymple, 2019: 34)] which subsequently became hereditary. Thus, after the death of Manikchand, his nephew Fatechand was conferred the title in 1922 CE by Emperor Muhammad Shah. Fatechand was the longest-reigning Jagat Seth. He was most intelligent, cunning, and extraordinarily wealthy. He had the power and cunningness to make or break a Nawab of Murshidabad. He served Murshid Kuli Khan (1717-27 CE) Nawab Sujauddin Khan (1727-39), Sarfaraz Khan (1739-40), and Alibordi Khan (1740-56) and after his death, in 1752 Seth Mahatab Rai became the third Jagat Seth who served Alibordi and Siraj Ud Daullah(1756-57).

Seth Manikchand and subsequent Jagat Seths were devout Jains and were the heads of Jain communities of the then Bengal, Bihar, and Orissa due to their strong connections with Mughal and Nawabi administration as well as their financial richness. Manikchand built a Jain temple at Mahimapur, on the outskirts of Murshidabad attached to his palace. Mount Pareshnath is one of the holiest places to Jains. Out of 24 Tirthankars of Jain religion, 20 got Nirvana here. It is located in Jharkhand in the district of Giridih. To the Jains, it is also known as Summet Pahar.

Successive generations of the family also sponsored religious pilgrimages to Mount Pareshnath which they restored, extended, and revitalized. The Jagat Seths' undertook extensive temple-building activities in Murshidabad as well as in Pareshnath mountain. For this purpose, Jagat Seth Manickchand arranged a large tract of rent-free land from emperor Muhammad Shah (Doogar, <http://faculty.washington.edu/doogar/Research/mbd.pdf> : 16).

The Advent of Sheharawali Jains in Murshidabad

The Sheherwali communities of Jain came into prominence after the fall of Jagat Seths in 1765 CE during colonial rule. Both Jagat Seth Mahatab Rai and his cousin Maharaja Swarup Chand who collaborated with the British during the battle of Plassey were imprisoned by Nawab Mirkasim in Munger fort and later shot to death by the order of Mirkashim (Dalrymple, 2019: 183).

One Bir Das of Duggar clan of Rajasthan and Jain who was a wealthy resident of Kishangarh in Rajputana, arrived Murshidabad “in the first half of the eighteenth century” and commenced business on his own, setting up as a banker. He had two sons, Buddh Singh and Ban Singh, both bankers as well. Buddh Singh in turn had two sons, Bahadur Singh and Pratap Singh (1781–1860). Pratap Singh vastly increased the family fortunes both through his banking activities and by the acquisition of zamindaris. Within a short time, he acquired extensive zamindaris all over Bengal and Bihar. During his time the leadership of the Murshidabad Jain community shifted from the Jagat Seth to the Dugars. Thereafter various Jain clans like Nahar, Dudhoria, Kotharis, and Nawlakhas came to Murshidabad from Rajasthan as bankers, money Lander, traders, and fortune seekers. Subsequently, various other clans came here.

In course of time, they earned immense wealth epitheted by common people as bottomless wealth. They constructed their residential kothis (palaces) in the twin town of Jiaganj and Azimganj (two cities located on either bank of Bhagirathi). Since they went to Murshidabad city for their official job they began to be called Saherwali Jains within the inner circle (Doogar, <http://faculty.washington.edu/doogar/Research/mbd.pdf> : 14).

Utilizing their fathomless wealth, they constructed several gorgeous, intricately designed, and beautiful temples at Jiaganj as well as Azimganj. The twin city due to the presence of temples became so popular to Jains that the city of Jiaganj began to be termed as Jiaganj Tirth and is a popular destination of Jain pilgrims till today (Doogar, <http://faculty.washington.edu/doogar/Research/mbd.pdf> : 20).

Jain temples of Murshidabad

The triangular land encompassed by Lalbagh at the apex, Jiaganj, and Azimganj in the remaining corner is called ‘Shri Murshidabad Tirth’ by the Jains of entire India and abroad (Doogar, <http://faculty.washington.edu/doogar/Research/mbd.pdf> : 22).

There are about fifteen Jain temples within this triangular space of Murshidabad Tirth. Throughout the year and on special occasions Jains throughout India and abroad visit Murshidabad Tirth. The details of the location of the temple wise are appended below

Mahimapur Lalbagh

1. Nasiur Parswanath Temple

This temple and the erstwhile palace at Mahimapur signify the commencement of Jainpower in Murshidabad. This temple was built by the first Jagatseth, Seth Manikchand in the first decade of the 18th century CE. In 1897 the temple along with the palace was destroyed due to a devastating earthquake. The present temple was constructed by descendants of Jagatseth Family

in 1899 -1900 AD. Architecturally it is a five-pinnaced temple about 45 ft high on Dalan structure the four surrounding very small pinnacles of Murshidabad Pancharatna style. The large central spire is onion-shaped, carination in the lower side, further lower it is constricted in the neck having the top portion sharp-pointed. In front, there is a large dalan type porch (Nat Mandir) open on three sides. It is of colonial style with beautiful serrated ionic columns.

Kathgola, Lalbagh

2. Adinath Temple

The Temple was constructed by Lakshmi Pat Singh Dugar (1835-1886 AD) of the Sheherwali Duggar clan of Jiaganj at the same time while constructing Kathgola Palace within the same boundary in 1873. It is also known as Paresh Nath Temple or Kathgola Temple. The temple is dedicated to Bhagavan Adiswar or Adinath. Moolnayak of this temple is a 90 cm white-colored idol of Bhagavan Adiswar. The idol is believed to be 900 years old.

The temple is completely renovated now. Architecturally it is a dalan style temple with several pinnacles on the roof of which three side-by-side pinnacles in the center are larger. The octagonal central spire of the three is surrounded by eight lotus bud-like smaller pinnacles appearing like Ang shikhara. In addition, there are three smaller pinnacles each in the front and backside of the central spire. The other two larger spires are octagonal and are five pinnaced. Four smaller pinnacles are there around each spire. The domes are straight octagonal lotus bud types with constricted necks downwards. The well-decorated dalan is about 15 feet high located in an elevated base reached through several staircases. Four porches are there on four sides of the temple building. Smaller spires over turret-like structures are there in two front corners of each

porch roof. The porches are supported by Corinthian pillars. Entablature and the Cornish are highly ornamental. The walls of the dalan are decorated by pilasters pedimented windows, stone images of gods, hanging wooden blanks, etc

Jiaganj

3. Dadasthan Jain Temple, Jiaganj

A Dadabari is a type of shrine, usually located near a Jain temple, and dedicated to one of the four Dādā Gurus revered by the Kharatara Gaccha sect. Dadabari is a type of shrine, usually located near a Jain temple, and dedicated to one of the four Dādā Gurus revered by the Kharatara Gaccha sect of the Svetambara Jains. The four Dādā Gurus are Jinadatta Sūri (1075-1154 CE), Jinacandra Sūri Maṇḍhārī (1140-1166 CE), Jinakuśala Sūri (1280-1332 CE) and Jinacandra Sūri II (1541-1613 CE). Dadabaris are constructed by the Kharatara Gaccha sect of Svetambara Jains. Accordingly, in Jiaganj also A dadabari in memory of guru Jinadatta Sūri was constructed by the same sect and resident of Jiaganj near Parswanath Jain Temple (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/D%C4%81d%C4%81bad%C4%AB>) at about more than 250 years ago as recorded and written in the entrance gate of the shrine.

The entire edifice, a large Rajasthani domed complex is located on an elevated platform. A flight of stairs led to the courtyard of the temple. The courtyard is enclosed by boundary wall. In every corner of the boundary wall there is a small domed turret like structure. The original temple is double storied and surrounded by circumambulatory path. The roof of square ground floor is supported by pairs of Doric columns (with small ornamentation in capital). The roof is enclosed by concrete railing. The entrance door of the sanctum where there is a marble image of Guru Jinn Dutt Suri seated in padmasana condition, has Rajasthani chhatri design.

4. Parswanath Temple Jiaganj

The temple located within the compound of Dadasthan was constructed in 1830 AD by Shree Sangha (organisation formed by different Jain Communities of Jiaganj) The Svetambara temple has been beautifully decorated with intricate designs. These stand as unique example of ancient art and boasts of the skills of the craftsmen. The walls and pillars of the temple are adorned with specimens of ancient art and paintings. The idol or the Lord is 38cm in height and is white in colour. It is seated in a padmasana posture. The idol has been beautifully carved from a single stone and looks very appealing. The smiling face of the Lord looks very calm and serene. The temple contains six stone images and two images of eight metals.

It is a Deul type temple of about 50 ft height . The deul emerges from the roof of the sanctum. The entire deul is of pancharatha type and temple like anga shikharas are there in four corners and mid wall of the deul . There is also Rajasthani style sukanasa with lion head, on the mid wall of pancharatha projections on all four sides. Also there are two ornamental temples behind all four sukanasa one above another. The roof of the sanctum has been extended in front giving it a Natmandir structure. There is Veranda in right side of sanctum and the Natmandir , supported by pairs of Doric columns. The interior of the temple is very intricately and beautifully decorated

5. Sambhab Nath Temple , Jiaganj

The temple was constructed in 1827 AD by Mukhsudabad Shree Sangha , an association of Jain Communities of Jiaganj. This temple is believed to have been built about 200 years ago but the icon is an ancient one. It is one of the “Panchtirthi” of Bengal. Several Jain families like Dugars, Nawlakkhas, Singghis, Bothras , Nahars came here from Rajsthan during later half of eighteenth century and settled here as it was near Murshidabad ,the then capital of Bengal . Through merchant banking and other trading activities they made immense fortune ,purchased zamindaris also. They made the village both prosperous and populous. These families had actively participated in various activities of social welfare and religious celebrations. They constructed number of jain temples in the twin town of Jiaganj and Azimgang . In the Jain parlour these two towns along with Nasipur is known as Murshidabad Tirtha. Sambhabnath Temple was constructed by them. The temple has three stone images and eighteen images made of astadhātu.

It is a flat roof building having Rajasthani architectural style. A shikhara is there in the central part of the roof emerged from the sanctum. Smaller turrets along with shikharas are there above the parapet of the roof. Still smaller shikhara structures are there in between the turrets over the parapet. The large entrance gate, windows in two sides of the gate is decorated with ornamental Rajasthani style arches. Rajasthani lattices are also there. The entire building is located on an elevated platform of about eight feet. A flight of stairs from base led to the temple floor.

6. Adinath Temple Jiaganj

In 1787 AD the temple was constructed by Shri Keshari Singh Chhajlani a Jain merchant and banker. The temple was constructed in Baluchar area of Jiaganj, from where the famous Baluchari Shari was crafted . The principal deity of the shrine is Adinath Rishavdeva. There is eleven Ashtadhātu (eight metals) and one stone image

Three storied structure first floor is much smaller only covering the sanctum. Five shikharas (spires) emerged from first floor roof resembling pancharathna style. Moreover, Large and

octagonal central shikhara and smaller corner roof shikharas also resembles contemporary Murshidabad pancharatna style. The shikhara is elongated lotus bud type with metallic pitchers one after another in top. Body of the shikharas are decorated.

7. Bimal Nath Temple Jiaganj

The temple was constructed in 1892 AD by Chatarpat Singji Duggar a scion of famous Duggar family of Jiaganj founder of several temples like Adinath temple of Kathgola, Sambhabnathji temple of Azimganj; Palaces like Kathgola palace, Bari Kothi, Jiaganjetc; educational institutes like Shri Pat Singh College, Dhannyakumari Girls College etc, in this temple there are eight astadhatu and seven stone images. Principle deity is Bimal Nath Swamy.

Rajasthani style of pointed shikhara over a Dalan structure. Three storied structure first floor is much smaller only covering the sanctum. Five shikharas (spires) emerged from first floor roof resembling pancharatna style. Moreover, Large and octagonal central shikhara and smaller corner roof shikharas also resembles contemporary Murshidabad style. The shikhara is elongated lotus bud type with metallic pitchers one after another in top. Body of the shikharas are decorated.

Azim Ganj

8. Dadabari Temple Azimganj

This temple of Dadaji Jin Dutta Suri (one of the four famous Jain gurus of Kharatara sect of Swetambar Jain community) was constructed by Shri Sangha (an association of Jain community of the area) in 1870. In this temple the images of Cossimbazar Neminath temple (which was destroyed by that time) Parasnath images from Jangipur and Jiaganj were brought in and established. Thirty-three stone images and eighteen astadhatu images are observed here.

It is a three storied highly decorated completely renovated temple located on a 4 ft elevated platform. A large arched gate is there attached to the porch veranda. Left and right wall of the temple including windows are highly decorated in Rajasthan style. In the middle of the ground floor roof octagonal elevated platform having designs of lotus petal in all eight sides is there. In the central of the octagonal elevated platform emerged another smaller octagonal cylindrical structure having small shikhara structure with amalaka and pitcher(kalas) above it.

9. Sawlia Parswanath Temple

This temple of Sawlia Parasnath was constructed by Shri Sangha (an association of Jain community of the area) in 1870 within the boundary of Dadabari Jiaganj. Main deity of the

temple is Pareshnath. A significant attraction of this temple is depicting an altarpiece of jina chaturvimshatika or jina chauvisi, represents 24 jinas carved together. The Parsvanatha icon as Mulnayaka is on the top of the octagonal step, while the figures of the other 23 jinas are depicted in the parikara (surrounded) manner in diminutive forms (<https://www.sahapedia.org/tracing-visual-culture-jains-early-modern-bengal>).

It is a Rajasthani Dalan type temple with shikharas in the roof. A single storied large rectangular building having several pointed shikharas located over the sanctums of different Gods worshipped in the building. The temple has a long veranda in front with a semicircular porch. The cusped arched gates are of Rajasthani style.

10. Sambhav Nathji Temple

In 1886 AD Rai Bahadur Dhanapat Singh Dugar a famous merchant Banker of the area erected the temple. The temple is having the largest Swetambar Jain idol (Sambhabnathji- 3rd Tirthankara) of 8 (eight) feet height in eastern India. Rai Bahadur Dhanpat Singh Duggar (Kathgola palace fame) was instrumental and financier of constructing a railway line from Nalhati to Azimganj for bringing the idol to temple site. In this temple there are 86 stone images, 184 images made of eight metals, four static and one image of gem panna (emerald).

It is a three storeyed about 45 feet five spired temple (Pancharatna). The first floor is smaller than the ground floor. Spires emerged from first floor roof are like lotus buds but neck is not very deep, octagonal and of deul type. Four spires are located in four corners of first floor roof and other is in central position. Each spire has four smaller spires on its four corners. Octagonal base of the spires is well designed and constructed in the middle. There are three more buildings (dalan) in the temple compound having a courtyard in the middle. One building is another temple located in left side of the Sambhab nath temple. This temple is also having five similar spires but all the five spires are located in a row in the flat roof of ground floor. The temple is located on an elevated base of about 10 feet which can be reached through flight of stairs. The front Veranda of the building can be entered through cusped arched entrances designed in Rajasthani style.

11. Shantinath Jain Temple

The temple was constructed by Gulab Kumari Bibi a pious lady of Singhi Jain clan of Azim Ganj in 1873 AD. The deity of the temple is Parswanathji. There are four stone two astadhatu and one sphatik idol in the temple. The oldest deity is of Samvat 1553 (Bothra, 2010) equivalent to 1497 AD.

It is a double storied Dalan type temple structure along with four watch tower like turrets having small domes above in four corners of the 1st floor roof. A deul like shikhara emerged from the middle of the roof –octagonal but not so decorated. The roof has battlement in all four sides. There is a porch attached to central door built up to the roof of first floor. Over the porch roof

there is a chhatri (Rajasthani cupola) like structure having three small domes of which side domes are still smaller.

12. Chintamani Parasnath Temple

The temple was constructed by Manhot Jain family of Azimganj in 1888 AD. The main deity here is 23rd tirthankara Parswanathji popularly known as Chintamani Parasnath. Shri Chintamani Parshvanath Bhagwan seated in lotus posture. In this temple there are 28 stone images and 42 astadhatu images. Though the temple is about 130 years old but some idols are 400/500 years old.

It is a three storied Building Main sanctum is in the ground floor. The first floor is smaller than the ground floor. All over the parapet of ground floor roof there are small ornamental domes and in four corners chhatri like structures with onion like domes. Over the first-floor roof emerged several shikharas as anga shikharas around a comparatively larger one in the centre. In front of the shikharas there are three Amalaka like structures of which the middle one is larger. First floor structure has two parts inside chamber and outside circumambulatory path along with five cusped arched gates on all sides.

13. Sumatinath Jain Temple

Sri Sumatinathji Temple, Azimganj was built in 1856 AD by Uttam Chandji Nahar and was rebuilt by Setab Chandji Nahar in 1897 AD. Nahar families are one of the Jain families of Azimganj Jiaganj who came from Rajasthan in late eighteenth century and made good fortune in commercial activities. The main deity of the temple is Sumatinathji. There are 7 stone, 28 Astadhatu and 3 precious stone images in the temple.

It is single storied dalan type construction. There are turrets in all four roof corners and battlement all over. A very small hexagonal cone like shikhara over the sanctum position.

14. Neminath Jain Temple

The present temple of Neminathji was constructed by Shri Sangha a trust formed by all the Jain families of Azimganj and Jiaganj in 1943 sambat (1886 AD) AD in place of the original temple which was constructed in 1793 AD and was submerged due to change of course of river Ganga. There are 28 stone, 19 Ashtadhatu and 3 precious stone images in the temple. The principal deity of Shri Neminathji, made of marble gilded with silver and gold plates, is placed on an illustrated pedestal. The central figure of the Neminathji appears between the figures of Krishna and Balarama, considered his cousins. This conforms to the traditional iconography of Neminathji

which shows a mutuality between the Brahminical and Jain pantheon (<https://www.sahapedia.org/tracing-visual-culture-jains-early-modern-bengal>).

It is a four storied structure; first floor is smaller than the ground floor. Similarly, second floor is smaller than first floor. Low height parapet all over the ground floor roof. Turrets are in four corners of the roof. First floor has two parts: inside chamber and circumambulatory path, The roof of first floor along the pradakkhin (circumambulatory) path is supported by Doric columns and wooden blank hanging from first floor ceiling. First floor roof is covered by battlements all over along with turrets in all four corners of the roof. Number of Shikharas emerge from the second-floor roof and all the shikharas are culminated in a point at the top. The topmost shikhara is slightly larger. All the shikharas combinedly form a triangular unified shikhara shape. There are another two-lotus bud like octagonal shikharas emerged from ground floor roof in two sides of the first-floor structure. These two shikharas have four smaller shikharas in four sides of each.

Conclusion

The Existing Jain temples of Bengal constructed eighteenth and nineteenth century in Bengal by the Jain Merchants who came here during Nawabi period and early colonial period are still very vibrant. These Jain temples unlike other medieval Hindu temples and mosques constructed in same period most of which are in very poor conditions, are very vibrant and lively. Regular maintenance and renovation works are taken up by the affluent Jain community. But in several cases, it has been observed that traditional structures have been modified during renovation and reconstruction. Another significant aspect of present-day Jain tradition is as follows:

Though Jainism flourished in Bengal in three phases but there are fundamental differences between first two phases and third phase on different counts: a) in first two phases Jainism spread and was established through Jain sages but in third phase Jainism has been established through traders and merchants, b) local people embraced Jainism and worshipped Jain deities in first two but in third only people from Rajasthan, already Jains, worshipped the Jain deities. Contemporary Jain gurus also did not try to preach Jainism amongst local people. The role of local people is only that of onlookers. c) Architecturally the third phase temples also are of Rajasthani styles. However, in small number of cases Bengali styles like Pancharatna was followed. Where as in second phase the Bengali shikhara styles temple (northern Indian Shikhara style temple has been modified to some extent in Bengal) are observed in most of the cases. First phase temples are not found. However, though there are several Jain temples all over West Bengal including Kolkata the significance of Jain temples of Murshidabad Tirth is greatest to the Jain communities of the world. They make it a point to visit the Jain temples of Murshidabad at least once in their life time. Moreover, the group of Jain temples of Murshidabad is also an important heritage of Bengal.

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